

Scatterplot for: EXP00024 2021-02-15 (Experiment)

Report date: February 15, 2021 15:01

X-axis = ocimum control 3333

Y-axis = trreated 5

Corr coeff = 0.458817

Slope = 0.435324, Intercept = 3.125657

Spot count = 152

